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Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in Agricultural Sector

White paper

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1. Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in Agricultural Sector

Growing crops and livestock is at the heart of the agricultural sector. The entire value chain in the agrifood industry aims to feed the world's population. In today's market, agribusiness is highly technologised and internationally connected to meet quality demands for food safety and product diversity. Social sustainability factors are becoming more important, represented by labels such as fair trade and organic. Geo-political tensions are threatening the security and resilience of globally interconnected agricultural supply chains.

In response to this threat, the European Commission is aiming to make food systems fairer, healthier and more environmentally friendly through the Farm to Fork Strategy:

"Putting our food systems on a sustainable path also brings new opportunities for operators in the food value chain. New technologies and scientific discoveries, combined with increasing public awareness and demand for sustainable food, will benefit all stakeholders."

The European Commission has launched the EU Cloud Edge IoT initiative to embrace the opportunities offered by new technologies for connectivity, sensing and data collection as well as analysis and predictions in the agricultural sector. With the funding programme focusing on cloud, edge and IoT, the European Commission aims to reduce dependencies on non-European cloud computing providers, harness the potential of multi-stakeholder open source communities and data-driven value chains².

We would like to explore the technological challenges and solutions that will enable a transition to sustainable and reliable food production in agricultural value chains. We will point out critical dependencies from non-European market players and highlight market pathways taken by the innovative European CEI solution providers.

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1 https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy_en

2 <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/europes-potential-edge-computing-supporting-industrial-innovation-through-large-scale-pilots>

2 Cloud Edge IoT in the agricultural sector

The agricultural sector is comparatively small in terms of employment and revenue. For Europe, it is strategically important and critical. According to the survey, conducted by IDC (see [Deliverable 1.2](#)), the adoption of Cloud Edge IoT in agricultural sector is currently lagging behind, however, it will accelerate over the next five years to narrow the gap with other sectors.

Cloud Edge IoT technologies are usually employed for asset tracking and monitoring (such as animal tagging (see Deliverables [1.3](#), [3.2](#))). With a large number of mobile assets across the farm, managing them is a major challenge. This includes remotely locating and monitoring equipment and livestock. The tracking devices and equipment are typically connected to centralised resources in the cloud or a data centre via short-range wireless, cellular, LPWAN or satellite connections. Edge gateways are used to collect, aggregate and pre-process data before transferring it to the cloud. Agricultural fields and facilities are located in rural rarely populated areas with limited connectivity, which may lead to deployment of edge computing resources in or near these facilities. In [IDC's survey](#), asset monitoring, maintenance and repair was cited as one of the top use cases. Despite the lack of connectivity, respondents intend to run more workloads in the cloud than at the edge.

Automation in the agricultural sector

The automation of agricultural equipment aims to reduce the need for human labour. Fully autonomous agricultural equipment would contribute to higher yields, lower labour costs, remote operation and ultimately higher profitability and sustainability. This requires sensors and actuators to be integrated into the mechatronic systems. On the software side, artificial intelligence (AI) is key to improving precision and enabling machines to make decisions despite the complexity of farming operations. In terms of the cloud-edge-continuum, on-board automation systems are at the edge, but usually combined with cloud solutions for management and updates.

Precision Farming

Another important application area for CEI is precision farming. These applications use collected field and crop data to control and adjust automated fertilising, watering, harvesting and seeding according to the real-time conditions. As a result, applications often integrate multiple data sources such as machine sensor data, soil condition information and weather data. Precision agriculture aims to increase crop yields and/or reduce the use of resources such as water, energy and pesticides.

This document presents innovative use cases and solutions that combine cloud edge and IoT for on-device automation and precision (smart) farming. It illustrates how the distributed data collection is used for optimisation of land machines, field monitoring and tools for decision support for farmers.

3 Digital transformation of the Agricultural Sector

The agricultural value chain involves a set of stakeholders: farmers and agricultural producers, technology and data providers, data intermediaries and service providers, government and regulatory bodies, financial and insurance services, research and academic institutions, and industry associations. Cloud Edge IoT technologies are a key backbone for building the infrastructure for collaboration and workflow of products and goods in complex food systems.

The successful deployment and adoption of Cloud Edge IoT in the agricultural sector will depend on overcoming the following challenges:

- ☞ The lack of infrastructure and connectivity in rural areas
- ☞ High cost pressure due to the considerably small market size for CEI in agricultural equipment and automation.
- ☞ Regulatory compliance and reporting due to considerable government subsidies.
- ☞ Resiliency of supply chains.

CEI for the agricultural sector is currently very immature, associated with a very small global market (<5B€), which is likely to remain small for at least the next decade. In fact, only large-scale industrial agriculture is suitable for the deployment of intelligent agricultural sensor networks. In most countries, and especially in many European countries, most agricultural operations are too small and do not have the financial capacity to support the installation of such IoT platforms, a situation that is likely to continue (see Far Edge Study)³.

3 <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ff35c457-8f3b-11ee-8aa6-01aa75ed71a1>

4 Approach and analysis methodology

In the following, we would like to illustrate which innovative solutions and Cloud-Edge-IoT technologies are already available on the market and how they can enable the digitalisation of the agricultural sector and respond to the challenges outlined above.

To understand the current state of this transformation process, we will look in to the CEI market dynamics in the Agricultural Sector, in particularly:

Who are the big tech players in the CEI market and which services do they offer?

- 🌿 How the big tech CEI players cooperate with big players from the Agricultural Sector?
- 🌿 Which players in the Agricultural sector provide new innovative solutions? And how these solutions contribute to the transformation in the Agricultural Sector?
- 🌿 Where are the major dependencies from the big tech players and the resulting risks? What are market pathways and opportunities for CEI companies in the Agricultural sector?

Figure 1: Cloud-Edge-IoT Building Blocks - Source: UnlockCEI

Are CEI and farmers and their suppliers ready for data sharing?

Together with our partners IDC and Bluspecs, we identified basic building blocks that depict possible Cloud-Edge-IoT configurations for the technical infrastructures and services.

Each of these building blocks represents a domain that may require significant development and innovation to enable widespread adoption of the applications in the CEI continuum.

To explore the potential for innovation in these areas, we conducted workshops, supplemented by in-depth interviews with industry experts, to assess the value proposition of the building blocks outlined. We asked questions about how their products, platforms and services would contribute to cost efficiency and innovation in the areas illustrated. We also discussed the level of demand-side adoption of data sharing, open source software and hardware architectures in the agricultural sector.

5 CEI market dynamics in the Agricultural sector

Farm information management systems, such as FarmNet 365⁴, respond to cost pressures and offer services that allow to automate documentation and minimise the administrative burden of regulatory compliance. Farmnet 365 apps automatically document all activities down to the minute, such as working hours and machine positions. Precision farming solutions create seed and fertiliser application maps by identifying differences in field vegetation and potential. This kind of Farm management systems are compatible with systems and APIs of the key market players such as for example CLAAS or John Deer.

Digital solutions such as 365FarmNet support fleets of land machinery from different manufacturers. The information for all machines and equipment remains in one piece of software. Farmers can get a complete overview of all movements, automatically document all actions and evaluate their processes in a networked way.

Farm information systems build the backbone for the currently evolving data-driven value chain that involves farmers, land machinery vendors, cloud-edge-iot infrastructure and connectivity providers, chemical industry suppliers of fertilizers and for the plants and for the crops and medicaments for animal stocks, market places, insurance and government authorities.

Companies in the food processing industry and their suppliers are interested in the quality of the crops and ingredients that will help them to deliver a high quality product.

Last but not least, trade and retail companies complete the value chain. At this point, it is worth mentioning the Schwartz Group⁵, which employs innovative solutions in retail and logistics. It is one of the players, particularly in Germany, that has created its own ecosystem and aims to digitise the entire value chain.

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4 <https://www.365farmnet.com/en/>

5 <https://gruppe.schwarz/>

6 AgriDataSpace – Common European Agricultural Data Space

Emerging Data Sharing Initiatives and Data Spaces (DSIs) across Europe have already recognised the potential of data collected, managed and processed using Cloud-Edge-IoT infrastructures. The Common European Agricultural Data Space (CEADS) will connect different stakeholders and provide data intermediary services that enable data sharing for B2B (Business-to-Business) and B2C (Business-to-Customer), but also with B2G (Business-to-Government) business relations. Innovative SMEs and startups (B2B) can pool the collected data provided by the DSIs using interoperable data catalogues and offer new, novel AI-based services and solutions. Public authorities (B2G) will also receive access the data via data catalogues in case of emergencies or for monitoring and reporting purposes.

The European project AgriDataSpace⁶ analysed the current landscape of DSIs which is depicted on the following map⁷. The DSIs address numerous subsectors starting with farming machinery providers (AgriRouter⁸), data collected during milk production (IDDEN⁹), viticulture (AgDataHub¹⁰). The data collected is typically stored on-premises in farm information systems or transferred to a centralised data lake running on a cloud computing infrastructure. The technology for data sharing is not yet fully mature, but the most prominent tools for data sharing are currently developed as open source and can also operate on the edge (see Eclipse Dataspace Components¹¹). Many of the Data Sharing Initiatives mapped in AgriDataSpace project, employ cloud-centric solutions offered by non-European hyperscalers (AWS¹², Azure¹³, Google¹⁴).

Connectivity and communication technologies play an essential role in collecting, processing and transmitting data from IoT sensors and resource-constrained devices in fields and farms, on-premises edge computing nodes and remote cloud computing data centres.

The following example use cases demonstrate potential market paths and benefits of Cloud-Edge-IoT infrastructures and solutions.

6.1 Operational Efficiency through Usage Profile Analysis of Agricultural Vehicles

AVL's approach to increasing operational efficiency and predictive diagnostics exploits usage profile analysis of agricultural vehicles. Such use cases have been implemented for two customer segments: agricultural vehicle OEM-s (Original Equipment Manufacturers) and agricultural fleet operators.

Cloud edge IoT technologies and infrastructure are already available on the market. However, due to given constraints in the automotive supply chain (e.g., coupling of hardware and software development) customers rarely benefit from this technology push. AVL aims to make these technologies accessible to its customers and implements use cases with high value proposition for fleet operators and vehicle OEM-s targeting the agricultural sector.

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6 The preparation action for the Common European Agricultural Data Space (CEADS)
7 <https://agridataspace-csa.eu/>
8 <https://agrirouter.com/>
9 <https://www.idden.org/>
10 <https://agdatahub.eu/en/>
11 <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.edc>
12 https://aws.amazon.com/iot-core/?nc1=h_ls
13 <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/iot-edge/about-iot-edge?view=iotedge-1.4>
14 <https://www.ibm.com/products/maximo/environmental-health-safety>

Scalable Digital Twin Concept Empirical Models from Observations

Figure 2. Cloud-Edge-IoT for operational efficiency by analysing the usage profile of agricultural vehicles –
Source: AVL B. Peischl, D. Brunner, M.Zivandinovic, G. Schagerl

The example CEI solution encompasses a backend which is either hosted at AVL as an on-premises solution or in a public cloud.

The core of the solution is the digital twin that replicates the physical entities and parts of the vehicle on the cloud side to make informed decisions about the vehicle, i.e., adjusting parameters that determine the operational efficiency of the vehicle or scheduling maintenance measures. Every vehicle has a number of sensors integrated into its powertrain. To sense their surroundings, the vehicles are also equipped with perception technology. The telemetry data stream is aggregated and pre-processed on board. It is then sent back to the scalable cloud at the back end. This data is used by the customer, for example, a vehicle OEM or a fleet operator, to make informed decisions about (1) the maintenance status vehicle/powertrain components and (2) the operational efficiency of the vehicle.

Another example is the use cases for cloud-based controls. For example, we create a model on the cloud side and then deploy it over the air to the vehicle – the so-called DevOps loop. This scenario is more complex because we must deal with a lot of heterogeneous devices in different vehicles.

Operational profile analysis

The digital twin concept illustrated above is central to determine the operational profiles of a vehicle. Operational profiles cover the aspects of a vehicle's operation, such as material handling, seeding, spreading and crop protection or grass harvesting and baling, and transport or maintenance. These usage profiles can have a significant impact on vehicle maintenance actions, vehicle uptime and the total cost of vehicle ownership.

Real-time Operation Profile Analysis

Figure 3: Real-time operation profile analysis – Source: AVL B. Peischl, D. Brunner, M.Zivandinovic, G. Schagerl

Real-time operation profile analysis brings the following three major benefits for the Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs):

- data-driven and informed decisions improve the sales structures that can be tailored to the operational modes of a vehicle.
- the collected and processed data is crucial for designing the next generation of the vehicles. It has an immediate impact for the vehicle OEM and the development team of the vehicle OEM.
- real time communication that truly leverages the full spectrum of the cloud-to-edge continuum and allows for optimizing maintenance schedules and adjustment of parameters influencing the operational efficiency (e.g., parameters that influence the fuel consumption).

Vehicle Working Mode Classification

Using a GPS device to detect whether a vehicle is on the road or in the field is technically simple but might become expensive for a large vehicle fleet. Due to the high-cost pressure in the agricultural market, AVL has developed a cheaper solution based on an AI-based classifier. The proposed solution involves a pre-trained 'power take-off' sensor data set combined with 'on the road' vs. 'in the field' information collected using a GPS device. The classifier with the pre-trained model was then deployed to many vehicles, saving the cost of GPS equipment.

This kind of cheap and scalable profile analysis allow for obtaining accurate operational profiles that in a further step are then used for performing predictive diagnostics, e.g., by exploiting the correlations between the specific profiles and the deterioration of powertrain / vehicle components.

The vast amount of data currently available is often underestimated. Information about the environment in which the vehicle is operating, such as road infrastructure, ground conditions and tyre pressures, is very important for keeping the total cost of ownership (TCO) low and increasing vehicle uptime.

In the recent past, AVL has developed a portfolio of data intelligence products that enable cost savings and improved performance for fleets of agricultural vehicles.

Open vs. closed source software and hardware components

Open-source components reduce the TCO of software development and allow these components to be tailored to agricultural and vehicle needs. However, a distinction should be made between open source for the infrastructure components and proprietary customized solutions that address specific customer needs.

The traditional hierarchical supplier structure in the automotive industry frequently conflicts with the collaborative nature of open-source software. However, adopting an ecosystem-centric approach based on open-source software principles is crucial as the open-source goes beyond reducing TCO for software development. In contrast to sectors where software plays a foundational role, the automotive supply chain favors in-house software development, which – to a certain degree – limits its competitive advantage. Distinguishing between differentiating (e.g., application-specific code) and generic technology (e.g., data spaces as a common soft infrastructure) is crucial, urging the industry to reassess its stance on collaboration and competition.

Data sharing and data spaces

The most critical part of upscaling data spaces is to give the customer a clear understanding of responsibility and sovereignty over the data. We are in the very early stages of Data Spaces entering the market. At present, farmers, fleet operators and OEMs share the data based on bilateral agreements. OEMs are reluctant to share data, mainly because of the exposure of IP (intellectual property), especially when it comes to sharing raw data that would allow the analysis of machines by competitors and used for marketing, which is their main concern.

Cloud computing in agricultural sector

10 years ago, a traditional agricultural OEM would not have been willing to store data in a cloud computing environment because of the security risks involved. Today, vehicle operators and OEM-s understand that a professionally hosted cloud environment can be as secure as an on-premise solution. European frameworks such as Gaia-X or Catena-X also aim at facilitation the data sharing process and at the same time prevent vender lock-ins.

7 Supporting rural and remote communities to get digitally connected (COMMECT EU project)

There is a large digital divide between urban and rural areas in terms of connectivity and availability of high performance and efficient mobile networks, which unfortunately still persists.

Firstly, telecom operators are not really interested in deploying infrastructure in rural areas, simply because there is no business case with many potential users, so they will not invest. Of course, it is much more difficult and costly to deploy network infrastructure in the countryside because there is no mature road infrastructure. Moreover, weather conditions, such as heat, wind and rain can have a greater impact on the hardware components. However, connectivity and network infrastructure is an important pillar: if there is no connectivity, there is no way for the rural community to be part of the digital transition. Without them, there would be no way to collect data from the IoT devices, and there would be no way to transmit the information to the cloud.

A connected network infrastructure is the first step in the digital transformation of the agricultural sector, and this is the main objective of the COMMECT project.

The project was launched in September 2022. It involves five living labs in different countries inside and outside Europe, exploring different specific sectors of the agri-food and agri-forestry vertical.

In all these different locations, using a co-creation approach, technology providers such as technical experts, satellite operators, but most importantly stakeholders such as farmers, people working in forests, machine operators and people involved in livestock transport can contribute with requirements for cloud edge IoT services and solutions.

The first living lab is in Luxembourg and it is focused on viticulture, which is one of the main sources of the national economy, as Luxembourg produces and sells wine locally and internationally.

The living lab in Denmark is addressing livestock transport, particularly for pigs. There is a big market in the country, since piglets from Denmark are transported all over Europe. The living lab in Norway focuses on the forestry sector. In the Mediterranean region inside and outside Europe, in Turkey and Serbia, the living labs are researching and developing network infrastructure for olive growing and sustainable agriculture respectively.

COMMECT covers different regions that may have different socio-economic backgrounds. A set of use cases have been identified in the different Living Lab, based on the needs of local end-users and stakeholders.

COMMECT's approach involves the integration of various terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks, as a single, one-size-fits-all solution would not work. The connectivity solutions cover cellular networks, which can be 3G, 4G and 5G if it is available, public or private 5G networks and non-terrestrial network such as the drone and satellites (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Overview Comnect - Source: Comnect

Different edge and cloud configurations were compared and benchmarked, because in some use cases it makes more sense to do processing closer to the device at the edge, while in others the data needs to be transferred to the cloud. There is no limitation to a particular technology, so COMNECT is adopting cellular, and also non-cellular technologies. In the specific case of IoT technology, COMNECT adopt NB-IoT and LoRa/LoRaWAN protocols.

Luxembourg: viticulture

The Living Lab in Luxembourg focuses on viticulture and aims to combine Remote Sensing (RS) data with Internet of Things (IoT) data (in-situ measurements) and to study how different connectivity technologies (LoRaWAN, satellite) could support wine growers in their decision-making.¹⁵

In the case of viticulture, COMNECT helps winegrowers to monitor microclimatic conditions. In two consecutive summers, there was a flood and then in 2021 and the following year, 2022, there was a drought: so the winegrowers had to deal with one extreme event, and then another.

The flood caused fungal diseases to spread, and at the same time it became clear that it would be very useful for the winemaker to have a digital decision support tool based on a digital twin. In the event of droughts, local regulations prohibit the irrigation of all plants, only the younger plants are allowed to be watered. Having a digital twin that specifically identifies the plants that are under water stress would help them to optimize their activity.

Digital twin

The digital twin for viticulture requires multiple types of data that incorporates different scales, images with different resolutions. The first layer integrates satellite imagery (RS) with a large scale map, the second layer incorporates drone data with improved accuracy. The final layer contains images from cameras mounted on the tractors (in-situ measurements). These layers allow a higher resolution image to be obtained closer to the crop.

¹⁵ <https://www.horizoneurope-comnect.eu/living-labs/1-luxembourg-digitalisation-of-viticulture>

Norway: connected forestry

In Norway, most of the country is covered by forests, which is the focus of the Living Lab. The lack of connectivity in the forest can be dangerous in this remote area, especially for activities such as felling trees. The living lab in Norway focuses on forestry and is equipped with temporary private 5G networks and edge solutions. A 5G-VINNI NEXT node provides connectivity to a geographically limited area in the middle of the forest. A network on wheels can provide connectivity to a geographically limited area, with high capacity, low latency and support for mMTC. The latter are all necessary requirements for a smart forest, both to provide forest surveillance and to support remote management of forest machinery.¹⁶

This kind of connectivity is needed to support situational awareness. Also in the “Connected Forestry” use case, imagery collected by flying drones is very useful. Ideally, the data is transmitted in real time over 5G. In addition, sensors in the forest can monitor soil and weather conditions.

In addition, the private 5G real-time communication networks allow a virtual reality tool to be provided for remote assistance in maneuvering the machines in safety-critical tasks and situations. The virtual reality tool operates on the near-edge and uses 5G core network for data transfer.

AI data analytics models running at the far edge data centers can detect fires or accidents in the forest. Data is also collected from various IoT devices and sensors that measure temperature and humidity in remote facilities. The devices and sensors are used in the forest to measure soil moisture or humidity.

This data can also be sent back to the near edge for further analysis and processing. Thanks to 5G, it is possible to collect data from both the drone and all the Raspberry PI-based sensors.

Finally, the rescue agencies can immediately get an alarm in case of fire in the forest.

Cloud-Edge-IoT infrastructures allow to provide connectivity and computing resources from IoT-devices and sensors in the field and transfer the data from different sources including drones into the cloud.

Denmark: connected livestock transport

The Living Lab in Denmark focuses on livestock (pig) transport and develops and tests solutions suitable for different operations (animal loading/unloading or over-the-route transport) using multiple communication technologies (public 5G, private 5G, WiFi 6). Several over-the-route 5G coverage assessments will be carried out, providing relevant snapshots of 5G coverage along the main transport routes and across several countries. In areas where there is no 5G coverage or roaming interference, satellite connectivity will be provided. Finally, the Living Lab is investigating the deployment of an on-demand local green broadband network with terrestrial or satellite backhaul, dedicated to providing on-demand coverage and/or capacity during the loading and unloading of animals¹⁷.

Animal welfare regulations require that pigs should only travel for a certain amount of time, with stops to rest on temporary farms before being transported to the final farm. Resting and journey times are usually recorded manually. The driver is responsible for ensuring that the pigs are in good health during transport. They should arrive at the destination as healthy as when they were loaded.

There is a need to monitor the pigs during loading and unloading and to count the pigs to check their health status. The animal transport trucks travel through different countries in a rural area without a stable network connection.

And the driver has to manually record information about the pigs’ condition. Transmitting the data

¹⁶ <https://www.horizoneurope-commect.eu/living-labs/2-norway-connected-forestry>

¹⁷ <https://www.horizoneurope-commect.eu/living-labs/3-denmark-connected-livestock-transport-1>

to the cloud would make it much easier to count and verify the health status and number of pigs.

AI analytics

A camera with real-time video transmission would allow an AI model to process the video data and determine the number of pigs and their health status, avoiding manual effort and costs.

Turkey – Smart Olive Tree Farming

The Living Lab in Turkey focuses on the olive grove and integrates a wide range of technologies (NB-IoT, eMTC, 5G NR and WiFi) to provide digital solutions for farmers, foresters and refugees. Social and economic integration will be ensured, in particular by training refugee women in olive cultivation. Data collected from sensors installed in the field feeds early warning systems that inform end-users of the most effective time to control diseases and pests. The use of early warning systems supports environmental sustainability and increases the yield and quality of the product through correct, timely and adequate control.¹⁸

The Smart Olive Tree Farming Living Lab focuses on the impact of climate change on olive production. Changing environmental conditions require tools and equipment to collect data and help detect new pests and insects based on image or video data. Based on the data analysis, the farming information system can trigger an action remotely to protect the olive trees from decease.

Serbia – Sustainable Agriculture and Preservation of Natural Environment

The Living Lab in Serbia focuses on digital agriculture and environmental protection in the municipality of Žabalj. It provides a common energy, connectivity and edge processing infrastructure with value-added services running on top of it. The services provide 1) digital farming (recommendations, decision support, autonomous control of irrigation process tailored to crops, vegetation period and general soil and weather conditions, taking into account potential limitations of energy production), 2) continuous monitoring of environmental parameters via a kit of battery-powered LoRaWAN/5G sensors to monitor operational parameters of irrigation systems and environmental conditions (air and water quality, noise) to support the preservation of the nature park and its biodiversity, 3) autonomous and remote control of energy, connectivity and edge processing infrastructure at the municipal level to optimise its use and ensure uninterrupted operation. Renewable energy installations will be equipped with LoRaWAN/5G infrastructure to enable local connectivity. Solar installations will be equipped with edge gateways to enable autonomous operation of the system.¹⁹

The Living Lab for Sustainable Agriculture and Preservation of the Natural Environment aims to encourage farmers to use natural resources for irrigation and optimising the yield, especially renewable energy sources, to power the Cloud-Edge-IoT infrastructure.

IoT devices and sensors are used to monitor climate conditions, the soil, how the crops are growing.

In many cases these devices collect so called small data. But in other cases, there is need to process the big data like, images and videos acquired from a camera which is mounted on a drone or from a tractor. And obviously, this data has to be processes at the edge and in other cases it should be transmitted to the cloud in to perform computationally demanding data analysis.

The Living Lab in Serbia demonstrates an infrastructure for a rural community that includes not only networking and communications, but also energy and computing resources.

The company SolarAgro produces affordable solar panels that can be moved on a mobile track. The solar panels can be moved on a track and be unfolded at appropriate location to power the

18 <https://www.horizoneurope-commect.eu/living-labs/4-turkey-smart-olive-tree-farming>

19 <https://www.horizoneurope-commect.eu/living-labs/5-serbia-sustainable-agriculture-and-preservation-of-natural-environment>

devices that are in the field.

A camera carries out a video surveillance to detect if someone damages the solar panels and devices. The portable power grid can power a weather station to monitor environmental conditions and control pumps and valves in an irrigation system for crops in the field. The connection is established using low-cost LoRaWAN technology.

The portable energy grid for the cloud edge IoT infrastructure can be shared between farmers in the same region. The collected data is transmitted via 5G to a cloud-based data analytics and decision support tool for farmers, which provides advice on when to irrigate, based on the conditions in the field. Farmers can ask for a recommendation for better management of fields, crops animal stock and fields.

Data Sharing

Data sharing has the potential to bring many benefits. The data collected from a particular farmer's field can be relevant to other farmers in the same region, or even to other farmers growing similar crops in another country.

There is huge potential, especially for small or less skilled farmers who may not have the ability or know-how to install IoT devices and sensors in the field. Data sharing is very important for future food security, because only by making all this data available to the actors in a value chain can better food security be ensured. However, many farmers or end users are not yet ready for data sharing.

There is fear that the data can be used against them, for example, if they use the wrong amount of fertilizers or they use a lot of pesticides. Or the data can expose a bad yield and another competitor will be able to getting advantage in higher prices.

A clear benefit and advantage of data sharing for example by using contractual agreements and providing access to services with high value proposition are helpful to gain and leverage the full potential of data. Offering money for sharing the data, or services that improve the production can reduce the fears of the farmers.

Different actors in the agricultural value chain would benefit from a marketplace that provides access to data. For example, farm data could be used by an insurance company to predict weather-related crop losses and the farmer can receive government support.

Farmers do not have a deep understanding of the communication technologies, providing connectivity and in most of the cases, they do not really care about the technical aspects. What matters is the service that helps to save effort and reduce costs. Therefore, COMMECT is developing a decision-making support tool (DST) which will advise and assist farmers and municipalities in making the best choice of connectivity infrastructure.

The tool will be able to advise, which connectivity technologies LoRaWAN, 5G, etc. are most appropriate for the specific use cases. The DST will also take into account socio-economic and environmental impact of the use cases. COMMECT also investigates collaborative business models aiming at having a positive socio-economic impact for several stakeholders of the agricultural value chain.

8 Conclusions and observations

The agricultural data-driven value chain involves different stakeholders from various vertical subdomains: farming, forestry, viticulture that employ Cloud Edge IoT infrastructures and solutions. Data Sharing Initiatives and the digital backbone of the agricultural sector, the Farming Information Systems employ cloud computing services of big tech providers such as AWS, Google and Microsoft, leaving limited room for European companies. Nevertheless, the European companies such as AVL provide more tailored edge computing and data intelligence solutions that bring substantial cost benefit for farmers and land machinery providers and operators. Additionally, open-source solutions allow to reduce the cost of ownership and avoid vendor lock-in.

The following market pathways for successful deployment and adoption of Cloud Edge IoT in the agricultural sector can be observed:

AgriDataSpace (Common European Agricultural Data Space) for cost efficient innovative solutions, resiliency of supply chains, regulatory compliance and reporting

- ✿ Enables data sharing for B2B (Business-to-Business) and B2C (Business-to-Customer), but also with B2G (Business-to-Government) business relations.
- ✿ Allows for data pooling for innovative SMEs and startups (B2B) that offer new, novel AI-based services and solutions using interoperable data catalogues.
- ✿ Provide access to data via data catalogues for public authorities (B2G) in case of emergencies or for monitoring and reporting purposes.

Risks: low readiness to share the data, immature tools for data sharing, cloud-centric DSIs and a high degree of dependence on big tech hyperscalers.

AVL – cost reduction using operational efficiency, profile analysis of agricultural vehicles and data intelligence

Benefits:

- ✿ Enables informed decisions about the vehicle, material handling, seeding, spreading and crop protection or grass harvesting and baling, transport or maintenance.
- ✿ Collects and analyses the sensor data to design the next generation of the vehicles.
- ✿ impact on the vehicle OEM and the development team of the vehicle OEM.
- ✿ Using data intelligence and AI solutions to replace and save costs for diagnostics and predictive maintenance to optimise service intervals.

Risks:

- ✿ OEMs are still reluctant to share the data.
- ✿ Lack of understanding how CEI technologies and data intelligence can help farmers save money.

Comnect – supporting rural and remote communities to get digitally connected

Benefits:

- ✿ Decision support tool helps winegrowers to monitor microclimatic conditions based on the digital twin.
- ✿ Private 5G real-time communication networks allow a virtual reality tool to be provided for remote assistance in manoeuvring the machines in safety-critical tasks and situations.

- 🌾 AI data analytics models running at the far edge data centers can detect fires or accidents in the forest.
- 🌾 A camera with real-time video transmission allows an AI model to process the video data and determine the number of animals (pigs) and their health status, avoiding manual effort and costs.
- 🌾 Based on the data analysis, the farming information system can trigger an action remotely to protect the olive trees from disease.
- 🌾 A portable energy grid for the cloud edge IoT infrastructure can provide connectivity and energy in a rural areas, the infrastructure can be shared between farmers in the same region.
- 🌾 The collected data is transmitted via 5G to a cloud-based data analytics and decision support tool for farmers, which provides advice on when to irrigate, based on the conditions in the field.
- 🌾 Farmers receive recommendation for better management of fields, crops animal stock and fields.

Risks: Connectivity devices and CEI infrastructure require additional investments.

The illustrated examples highlight how Cloud Edge IoT infrastructures and services help to save effort and reduce costs. However, in agricultural sector a collaborative approach to shared infrastructure and devices, with government support, would be the best way to adopt cloud edge IoT technologies and infrastructure in rural areas.

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